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A HOARD OF LATE ROMAN AND VISGOTHIC GOLD

4. Cuna, Seville 1972

by

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A HOARD OF LATE ROMAN AND VISGOTHIC GOLD

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4. Cuna, Seville 1972

[PLATES 52–55]

*Dep. c.*555

77 *A*

Disp. Seville Archaeological Museum

Abstract. Although found in 1972 this hoard of 41 late Roman solidi and 36 Visigothic tremisses has never been properly published. This paper presents the first catalogue of these coins which will be analysed in depth by the author in a forthcoming work. The hoard is believed to have being concealed around the middle of sixth century, probably at the time of the war between Agila and Athanagild between 552 and 555.

Introduction

A hoard of 77 solidi and tremisses was found by accident in 1972 in a central street in Seville, one of the most important cities in Southern Spain during Antiquity. During the construction of a building at 46 Cuna a small pot of coins fell out of a wall. The workers divided up the 77 coins among themselves – the original number was 78 but one of the coins was lost – but suspicions were aroused when somebody tried to sell them at a very popular antique market in the city known as ‘El Jueves’. The case was brought to court but only resolved some years later. The find lacks a precise archaeological context, but we know that the hoard was found near one of the Guadalquivir’s old riverbanks, for until the tenth century, the river ran right through the centre of what is today the modern city.²

Publication history

Some of the story surrounding the hoard was published in local newspapers,³ but not before numismatists had started looking at the find. C. Fernández Chicarro, who was at the time the director of Seville’s Archaeological Museum, published a brief description of the coins and a picture of the whole assemblage. A few years later, X. Barral did the same and included the hoard in his book on Visigothic finds,⁴

¹ Research projects: ‘La invención del pagano: Las fronteras de la identidad religiosa en el mundo tardoantiguo’ (HAR-2014-51946). I would like to thank Peter Bartlett and Fernando López-Sánchez for reading this paper and also for their interesting suggestions and detailed comments.

² According to E. García-Vargas, ‘La Sevilla tardoantigua’, in *Sevilla Arqueológica* (Seville, 2015), p. 184, the western pavement of calle Cuna – where the hoard appeared – has been archaeologically documented as an ancient river bank.

³ *ABC de Sevilla* (19-9-1972), p. 31; *ibid.*, (6-5-1973), *ibid.*, p. 9; (3-5-1975), *ibid.*, p. 85; *La Vanguardia Española* (20-9-1972), p. 13.

⁴ X. Barral, ‘Trésor de monnaies d’or des Ve et VIe siècles, trouvé à Séville’, *BSFN* 30, 4 (April 1972), pp. 749–52, *id.* *La circulations des monnaies suèves et visigotiques, contribution à l’histoire économique du royaume visigot* (Zürich-Munich, 1976).

followed by F. Mateu y Llopis in 1979.⁵ None of these publications contained a full classification of the pieces, and the only photographs in print were those taken by the police, which had been the basis of the hoard's inclusion in several scholarly papers.⁶ The hoard was kept for years in a bank safe, which made access to it very difficult. Only recently, after long and costly efforts, has it been transferred to the Seville's Archaeological Museum where it is available for study.⁷

The composition of the hoard

<i>Denomination</i>	<i>Emperor/In the name of</i>	<i>No.</i>	<i>Total</i>
Official Solidi	Honorius (393–423)	39	41
	Arcadius (395–408)	2	
Pseudo-imperial Visigothic Solidi	In the name of Anastasius (491–518)	1	13
	In the name of Justin I (518–27)	1	
	In the name of Justinian I (527–65)	11	
Pseudo-imperial Visigothic Tremisses	In the name of Anastasius (491–518)	1	23
	In the name of Justin I (518–27)	7	
	In the name of Justinian I (527–65)	15	
<i>Total</i>			77

*Fig. 1. Composition of the Seville hoard.*⁸

All of the official solidi are of the same type, with pearl-diademed, draped, and cuirassed emperor's bust facing right on the obverse and the emperor standing right, holding a crowned Victory on globe in his left hand and a *vexillum* in his right, and his left foot on a bound captive on the reverse (*RIC* 10, nos 1205–1206). These official solidi were all struck at Mediolanum (Milan). The 13 pseudo-imperial Visigothic solidi copy typologies from later imperial solidi: frontal bust of emperor, head facing slightly to the right, holding spear over his right shoulder and a shield on his left arm decorated with the motif of a horseman spearing a soldier. On the reverse, Victory standing left, holding a long jewelled cross.⁹

One of the most remarkable features of this set of coins is its composition, which conflates official solidi of Honorius and Arcadius dated in the first third of the fifth century on the one hand, and mid to late sixth century coins on the other. The older

⁵ F. Mateu y Llopis, 'Hallazgos monetarios (XXV)', *Numisma* 156–161 (1979), pp. 121–47.

⁶ J. Lafaurie, 'Trésor de monnaies du VI^e siècle découvert à Alise-Sainte-Reine en 1804', *RN* 25 (1983), p. 116; *RIC* 10, p. cxi; J. Lafaurie and C. Morrisson, 'La pénétration des monnaies byzantines en Gaule mérovingienne et visigotique du VI^e au VIII^e siècle', *RN* 29 (1987), p. 42; J. Lafaurie, 'Monnaies frappées en Gaule', in *Clovis, histoire et mémoire. Actes du Colloque International d'Histoire de Reims, du 19 au 25 septembre 1996 (Vol. 1–2)* (Paris, 1997), p. 779; J.M. Peixoto Cabral and D.M. Metcalf, *A moeda sueva. Suevic Coinage, Anexas Nvmmus* 4 (Porto, 1997), p. 53.

⁷ I wish to thank C. San Martín and A. Navarro, former and current director of the Archaeological Museum, for allowing us access to the hoard on several occasions.

⁸ For Merovingian attributions of Pseudo-Imperial tremisses similar to these found in Gaul see Lafaurie, *Monnaies frappées en Gaule*, pp. 769–802.

⁹ This iconography was originally struck by Galla Placidia in the East and had a good reception in the Western mints (*RIC* 10, p. 162). This was the only typology used in the Visigothic solidi from the time of Anastasius (491–518) until Leovigild's reign (572–86), when the tremisses became the sole denomination struck by the Visigoths.

coins are clearly more worn. The total weight of the hoard is 268.84 grams, 66.36% (178.40 grams) of which is made up of official coinage. The average weight of the official solidi in the hoard is 4.35 grams, somewhat below the standard weight of 4.548 grams. The average weight of the pseudo-Imperial solidi is 4.39 grams, though that of the imitations of Justinian I, the most numerous category, is 4.44 grams (Fig. 2).

In general the diameter of the official solidi is smaller than that of the Pseudo-Imperial ones (Fig. 3).

Denomination	No. of coins	Min. weight	Max. weight	Mid. weight	Aver. weight
Official Solidi	41	4.08	4.50	4.36	4.35
Pseudo-imperial Visigothic Solidi	13	4.00	4.49	4.43	4.39
Pseudo-imperial Visigothic Tremisses	23	1.41	1.47	1.45	1.45

Fig. 2. Weight of the coins in the Seville hoard (grams)

Denomination	No. of coins	Min. diam.	Max. diam	Mid. diam	Aver. diam
Official Solidi	41	20.28	21.63	20.96	21.03
Pseudo-imperial Visigothic Solidi	13	21.12	22.77	21.63	21.77
Pseudo-imperial Visigothic Tremisses	23	13.98	15.83	15.12	15.09

Fig. 3. Diameter of the coins in the Seville hoard (millimeters)

The die axis is far more regular on the official coins. (Fig. 4)

Fig. 4. The axial position of the coins in the Seville hoard (h)

The official solidi, struck during the reign of Honorius, circulated widely in Spain beyond the narrow period of AD 409/11¹⁰, as can be deduced from the composition of other hoards from the Iberian Peninsular. The occurrence of these coins in the south could be related to the Empire’s attempt at controlling the Straits of Gibraltar, and

¹⁰ Cabral and Metcalf, *A moeda sueva*, p. 53. See also S. Fischer and F. López Sánchez, ‘Subsidies for Rome? Eastern solidi in the Western Empire’, forthcoming.

not necessarily with direct invasion.¹¹ In addition, most of the official and unofficial solidi in the names of Honorius and Arcadius found in the Iberian Peninsula bear the mintmarks of the city of Milan (**M-D**),¹² where all the official solidi in the present hoard were struck.

Nonetheless the composition of the hoard is very unusual for the Iberian Peninsula; indeed there is only one recorded comparable hoard. This is the so-called ‘Hoard of Sierra-Tejea’, which was apparently found in Extremadura. The only reference is a brief note by Arthur Engel whose account of the Gago collection says it contained ‘*quelques spécimens fort curieux d’une trouvaille de sous d’or byzantins de style barbare, faite à Sierra-Tejea*’.¹³ He also claimed that on some of these coins there was an **N** positioned vertically at the end of the reverse legend. Indeed, in the Gago Collection, which is now in the Municipal Archive in Seville, there are two Visigothic imitation solidi struck in the name of Justin I and Justinian I, respectively, which correspond to this description.¹⁴ We know nothing of the remaining coins in the hoard or whether there were any Roman coins among them. Other known Visigothic hoards – El Real de La Jara, La Hermida, Zorita de los Canes¹⁵ and Merida – are dated later, to the reign of Leovigild (568–86).¹⁶

Mixed hoards are more common in France, and their composition combines official coins with imitations struck by the different Germanic groups, as well as the Visigoths. As in the Iberian Peninsula, most finds of Visigothic coins were discovered in the nineteenth century and their contents dispersed.¹⁷ The hoard of Alise-Sainte-Reine 1804 deposited c.550, although more or less contemporary with the present hoard, could hardly be more different. Three of its six Byzantine pieces were minted in Constantinople, two by Leo I (457–74) and one by Anastasius.¹⁸ Furthermore, the Alise hoard does not seem to have included solidi imitations, although it featured many Ostrogothic, Burgundian and Visigothic pseudo-imperial tremisses.¹⁹ The reports on the Chinon, ante 1882, hoard (dep. c.530), composed of 81 ‘solidi’, does not reveal whether the hoard contained any official Byzantine coins, although a solidus of Zeno (474–91) ‘*fort barbare*’ is mentioned.²⁰ It seems to have included

¹¹ Fischer and López Sánchez, ‘Subsidies for Rome?’, forthcoming.

¹² Fischer and López Sánchez, ‘Subsidies for Rome?’, forthcoming.

¹³ A. Engel, ‘Notes sur les collections numismatiques de l’Espagne’, *Bulletin mensuel de Numismatique et d’Archéologie* 6 (1886–90), p. 24. See also X. Barral, *La circulation*, p. 80. This hoard is also recorded by F. Mateu y Llopis, ‘El arte monetario visigodo. Las monedas como monumentos (Un ensayo de interpretación)’, *Archivo Español de Arqueología* (1943), p. 188.

¹⁴ F. Perez Sindreu, *Catálogo de monedas y medallas de oro. Gabinete Numismático Municipal* (Seville, 1980), nos 43–44.

¹⁵ For the first three hoards see Barral, *La circulation*, p. 82 ff. R. Pliego, *La moneda visigoda*, vol. I, p. 83 ff. revises the descriptions as well as discussing the Merida hoard.

¹⁶ Pliego, *La moneda visigoda*, I, p. 231.

¹⁷ See for example the hoard of Reignac, found in 1864 which contained eight solidi, of which only two, kept by the Société archéologique de Touraine, are known: one solidus of Marcian struck in Constantinople and one Frankish imitation to the name of Justin I (see Lafaurie and Morrison, ‘La pénétration des monnaies byzantines’, p. 48).

¹⁸ For the presence of solidi struck in Constantinople found in fifth century hoards in the Western Empire, Italy in particular, see Fischer and López Sánchez, ‘Subsidies for Rome?’, p. 9, forthcoming.

¹⁹ Lafaurie, ‘Trésor de Alise-Sainte-Reine’.

²⁰ Lafaurie and Morrison, ‘La pénétration des monnaies byzantines’, p. 48.

Ostrogothic, Burgundian and Visigothic imitations struck in the name of Anastasius and Justin I. More interesting perhaps is the recent Roujan hoard²¹ (deposited *c.* 530) consisting of 28 pieces, among which there is one Byzantine solidus in addition to imitation solidi and tremisses struck in the name of Anastasius and Justin I by the Ostrogoths, Burgundians, Franks and, especially, the Visigoths.

In conclusion, the presence of official solidi of Honorius and Arcadius in the Seville hoard, which are much earlier than the latest coins in the hoard, sets this hoard apart from its contemporaries.²² In this regard, while more than half of the pieces in the Seville hoard are Roman (41 against 36), the number of official coins in other hoards is much smaller, even when they occur. On the other hand, the other assemblages tend to be chronologically tighter and often include Eastern mints. The presence of graffiti on some of these coins, especially the earliest ones, has been described as characteristic of the period.²³ Although these aspects are being analysed in detail elsewhere, it seemed that they should at least be mentioned here.²⁴

The hoard in its historical context

As previously mentioned, the latest coins in the Seville hoard were struck in the name of the Emperor Justinian I. Although the chronological span is wide (up to five Visigothic kings issued coins during Justinian I's reign),²⁵ I would argue that the hoard was deposited towards the end of this period, based on the stylistic similarities of some of the coins in the hoard with those minted by Leovigild in the name of Justin II (565–78). In this regard, it is very significant that the hoard contains no coins in the name of the latter emperor, which confirms a date before the reign of Leovigild, and probably also Liuva I (567–72).²⁶

In sum, we should date the hoard to the mid-sixth century, sometime around the death of Theudis (548) or, more likely, in the convulsed years of conflict between Agila and Athanagild (552–5). Let us remember that the latter, an important member of the nobility, managed to snatch the crown from the legitimate king, Agila (549–55), with the support of other aristocrats. The fight was made worse by the intervention, in favour of the usurper, of Justinian I, who was at the time trying to restore the West

²¹ M. Dhénin and Ch. Landes, 'Vingt-cinq monnaies d'or de l'antiquité tardive au Musée archéologique H. Prades de Lattes (Hérault)', *La Revue du Louvre et des Musées de France* 5–6 (1994), pp. 7–8. This hoard is being re-examined by V. Geneviève and Ruth Pliego.

²² Childeric's hoard in Tournai also falls, in my opinion, within the same mixed category as Seville's, although they are different in many ways. See S. Fischer and L. Lind, 'The coins in the grave of King Childeric', *Journal of Archaeology and Ancient History* 14 (2015), pp. 2–36.

²³ H. Holzer, 'Graffiti on Roman solidi', *The Numismatist* 53 (1940), pp. 850–2; id. 'Christian and secular graffiti on Late Roman and Byzantine gold pieces', *Numismatic Review* 2 (1944), pp. 33–47. See also G. Bijovski, 'A hoard of Byzantine solidi from Bet She'an in the Umayyad period', *RN* 158 (2002), pp. 161–227.

²⁴ The coins from the hoard have been analysed by XRF in the Centro Nacional de Aceleradores (Seville), and P. Bartlett has also measured their specific density.

²⁵ See Pliego, *La moneda visigoda*, I, p. 75, where the author establishes the equivalence between Visigothic and imperial reigns.

²⁶ After the death of Athanagild, there was an interregnum of several months until Liuva I was elected king in 567. Shortly after this, Liuva split the government of the kingdom with his brother Leovigild, who ruled most of Hispania from Toledo while Liuva was based in Narbonne (*c.* 572).

to the empire.²⁷ The final battle took place in Hispalis (modern Seville) in 555, when the followers of Agila, decided to murder the king and join the cause of Athanagild.²⁸ Thus Athanagild (555–67) won the throne but had to give away a narrow strip of coastland between Cádiz and Valencia, in payment for the Byzantine intervention in his favour. This territory was turned into the Byzantine province of Spania, and did not return to Visigothic rule until the reign of Suintila (621–31).²⁹

CATALOGUE

OFFICIAL ROMAN SOLIDI

HONORIUS (393–423) Mint of Mediolanum (Milan)

Obv. Pearl-diademed, draped and cuirassed bust right. **DNHONORI-VSPFAVG**

Rev. Emperor standing right, holding standard and Victory on globe, trampling on captive. **VICTORI-AAVGGG**; In exergue **COMOB**; in field to left **M**, to right **D**
RIC 10, p. 318, no. 1206.

1.	4.50 g;	20.84 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8621.	
2.	4.44 g;	21.30 mm;	1 h.	Inv. no. 8635.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
3.	4.43 g;	21.50 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8617.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
4.	4.43 g;	20.98 mm;	12 h.	Inv. no. 8613.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
5.	4.43 g;	20.88 mm;	12 h.	Inv. no. 8610.	Scratched on obverse.
6.	4.42 g;	21.00 mm;	12 h.	Inv. no. 8633.	Scratched on obverse.
7.	4.41 g;	21.43 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8607.	Scratched on obverse.
8.	4.41 g;	21.39 mm;	12 h.	Inv. no. 8637.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
9.	4.41 g;	20.96 mm;	7 h.	Inv. no. 8619.	Scratched on reverse.
10.	4.41 g;	20.93 mm;	12 h.	Inv. no. 8611.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
11.	4.40 g;	21.48 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8631.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
12.	4.40 g;	21.12 mm;	12 h.	Inv. no. 8608.	
13.	4.39 g;	21.63 mm;	12 h.	Inv. no. 8622.	Scratched on obverse.
14.	4.39 g;	21.23 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8639.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
15.	4.38 g;	21.41 mm;	7 h.	Inv. no. 8632.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
16.	4.38 g;	20.85 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8605.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
17.	4.37 g;	20.79 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8620.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
18.	4.36 g;	20.96 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8641.	Scratched on obverse.
19.	4.36 g;	20.84 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8626.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
20.	4.36 g;	20.70 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8628.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
21.	4.35 g;	21.13 mm;	12 h.	Inv. no. 8612.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
22.	4.35 g;	20.87 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8614.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
23.	4.35 g;	20.66 mm;	6 h.	Inv. no. 8615.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
24.	4.34 g;	21.29 mm;	1 h.	Inv. no. 8638.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.
25.	4.33 g;	20.95 mm;	12 h.	Inv. no. 8636.	Scratched on obverse and reverse.

²⁷ The traditional date of the Byzantine incursion (551 or 552) has been recently revised to 554 (see J. Fossella, “‘Waiting only for a pretext’: A new chronology for the sixth-century Byzantine invasion of Spain”, *Estudios bizantinos* 1 (2013), pp. 30–8). See M. Vallejo, *Hispania y Bizancio: Una relación desconocida* (Madrid, 2012), pp. 147ff.

²⁸ Isidore of Seville, *Hist. Goth.*, XLVI, 3–14.

²⁹ For the archaeological reflection of this province see J. Vizcaino’s, *La presencia bizantina en Hispania (siglos VI–VII). La documentación arqueológica* (Murcia, 2009).

26. 4.33 g; 20.28 mm; 12 h. Inv. no. 8634. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 27. 4.32 g; 21.04 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8625. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 28. 4.31 g; 21.56 mm; 12 h. Inv. no. 8640. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 29. 4.31 g; 20.96 mm; 12 h. Inv. no. 8629. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 30. 4.31 g; 20.88 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8630. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 31. 4.30 g; 20.93 mm; 5 h. Inv. no. 8618. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 32. 4.30 g; 20.78 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8603. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 33. 4.29 g; 21.14 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8604. Scratched on obverse.
 34. 4.28 g; 21.39 mm; 11 h. Inv. no. 8627. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 35. 4.28 g; 20.86 mm; 12 h. Inv. no. 8624. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 36. 4.27 g; 20.80 mm; 12 h. Inv. no. 8623. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 37. 4.26 g; 20.72 mm; 12 h. Inv. no. 8606. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 38. 4.18 g; 20.90 mm; 12 h. Inv. no. 8616. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 39. 4.08 g; 20.47 mm; 1 h. Inv. no. 8609. Scratched on obverse and reverse.

ARCADIUS (395–408)

Solidi

- Obv.* Pearl-diademed, draped and cuirassed bust right. **DNARCADI-VSPFAVG**
Rev. Emperor standing right, holding standard and Victory on globe, trampling on captive. **VICTORI-AAVGGG**; in exergue **COMOB**; in field to left, **M**, to right **D**
RIC 10, p. 318 no. 1205.
 40. 4.41 g; 20.96 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8643. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
 41. 4.37 g; 21.30 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8642. Scratched on obverse and reverse.

VISIGOTH SOLIDI AND TREMISSIS

IN THE NAME OF ANASTASIUS (491–518)

Solidus

- Obv.* Helmeted facing bust with spear in right hand. **DNANASTA-SIV-SPFAVG**
Rev. Victory standing left holding long jewelled cross. **VICTORI-ΛΛVCCCA**; in exergue **COMOB**. Star in right field.
 Similar to Reinhart 1938, p. 134, no. 128.
 42. 4.00 g; 21.25 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8644. Scratched on obverse and reverse.

Tremissis

- Obv.* Laureate bust right. Cross on breast. **DNVNVATS-I-NAVSPPAVC**
Rev. **ICTIAIA-Λ-ICV?TOIVΛ**[?]; in exergue **CONOC**
 Similar to Tomasini, p. 194, no. 82.
 43. 1.47 g; 15.01 mm; 5 h. Inv. no. 8657. Small scratch on reverse.

IN THE NAME OF JUSTIN I (518–27)

Solidus

- Obv.* Helmeted facing bust with spear in right hand. **DNIVSTIN-V-SPPAVC**
Rev. Victory standing left holding long chi-rho cross. **VICTORI-AAVCCC**; in exergue **CONOB**. Star in left field; **N** in right field.
 Similar to Reinhart 1940–1, pl. 7, nos 11–12.
 44. 4.29 g; 21.34 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8645.

Tremisses

- Obv.* Laureate bust right. Cross on breast. **ONIVSTI-NVSPVAC**
Rev. Victory walking right holding wreath. **VIOTON-ΛVCTSTOR**; in exergue **CONOB**
 Tomasini, p. 207, no. 197 var.
45. 1.46 g; 14.59 mm; 5 h. Inv. no. 8667.
- Obv.* **ONIVSTI-NVSPFVAC**
Rev. **VICTORI-VCTSTOR**; in exergue **CONOB**
 Tomasini, p. 207, no. 199 var.
46. 1.45 g; 13.98 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8660.
- Obv.* **ONIVSTIN VSPPAVC**
Rev. **SVICTORVA-Λ-CVSTORVA**; in exergue **CONOB**
Obv. Tomasini, p. 201, no. 146 var.; *rev.* Similar to Tomasini, p. 200, no. 133.
47. 1.45 g; 14.94 mm; 4 h. Inv. no. 8678.
- Obv.* **ONIVSTI-NVSPFVAC**
Rev. **VICTORVA-ΛCVSTORVA**; in exergue **CONOB**
 Tomasini, p. 202, no. 149.
48. 1.44 g; 15.50 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8658. Scratched on obverse and reverse. Same dies as no. 49.
49. 1.44 g; 14.91 mm; 5 h. Inv. no. 8676. Scratched on obverse and reverse. Same dies as no. 48.
- Obv.* **OVITV-VNICSIC**
Rev. **VCT-''-VRIAC**; in exergue **CCONO**
 Tomasini - .
50. 1.42 g; 15.20 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8670.
- Obv.* **ONIVSTI-NVSPPAVC**
Rev. **ICTORIA-Λ-CV-STORVC**; in exergue **CONOIB**. Star in left field.
 Tomasini, p. 208, no. 211 var.
51. 1.44 g; 14.73 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8668.

IN THE NAME OF JUSTINIAN I (527–65)

Solidi

- Obv.* Helmeted facing bust with spear in right hand. **IVSTI-II-IIII**
Rev. Victory standing left holding chi-rho cross. **VICTORI-I-ΛΛVCCC**; in exergue **CONOB**. Star in left field.
 Reinhart 1940–1, pl. 8, no. 11.
52. 4.41 g; 22.49 mm; 7 h. Inv. no. 8646. Very worn reverse die.
- Obv.* **DNIVSTI-N-NAIIC**
Rev. **VICTORII-ΛΛVCCC**; in exergue **CONOB**. Star in left field; **N** in lower right field.
 Similar to Reinhart 1940–1, pl. 8, no. 6.
53. 4.40 g; 22.38 mm; 5 h. Inv. no. 8647.
- Obv.* **IDINVST-II-IIAN**
Rev. **IVNTORI-NVAVCCCI**; in exergue **CONOB**. Star in left field.
 Not in Reinhart.
54. 4.43 g; 21.12 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8648. Scratched on obverse, very rusty die on obverse and reverse.

- Obv.* **DNIVSTIIV-IV-SPPAVC**
Rev. **VICTORI-ΛΛVCCCA**; in exergue **COMOD**. Victory holds long jewelled cross; star in right field.
 Not in Reinhart.
 55. 4.42 g; 22.27 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8649. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
- Obv.* **DINV?T-NN-ANIC**
Rev. **VICTOR-I-IAAVCCCI**; in exergue **CONOB**. Blundered cross; star in left field.
 Not in Reinhart.
 56. 4.47 g; 21.68 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8650. Same dies as no. 57.
 57. 4.43 g; 21.30 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8651. Same dies as no. 56.
- Obv.* **DNIV?T-IN-NANI**
Rev. **VICTOR-I-ΛAVCCC**; in exergue **CONOB**. Star in left field; N in lower right field.
 Similar to Reinhart 1940–1, pl. 8, no. 5.
 58. 4.42 g; 21.52 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8652. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
- Obv.* **DNIVSTI-NN-ANI**
Rev. **VICTOR-I-ΛAVCCC**; in exergue **CONOB**. Star in left field.
 Similar to Reinhart 1940–1, pl. 8, no. 10.
 59. 4.45 g; 21.28 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8653. Very worn and rusty dies.
- Obv.* **DNIV?TI-NN-ANI**
Rev. **VICTOR-I-ΛAVCCC**; in exergue **CONOB**. Star in left field.
 Similar to Reinhart 1940–1, pl. 8, no. 10 (same obverse die).
 60. 4.45 g; 22.00 mm; 5 h. Inv. no. 8654.
- Obv.* **DIIVVST-N-NAVI**
Rev. **VICTORI-ΛAVCCCI**; in exergue **CONOB**. Star in left field.
 Not in Reinhart.
 61. 4.49 g; 21.63 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8655.
- Obv.* **DIIV?T-III-NAII**
Rev. **IVITOR-IAAVCCCI**; in exergue **COIIOB**. Victory holds long plain cross; star in left field.
 Not in Reinhart.
 62. 4.47 g; 22.77 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8656. Scratched on obverse and reverse.

Tremisses

- Obv.* Laureate bust right. Cross on breast. **DNIVSTINI-ANVSWIIC**
Rev. Victory walking right holding wreath. **V-ICTOIV-VTONAVI**; in exergue **CONO**
 Tomasini, p. 213, 259 var.
 63. 1.45 g; 15.60 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8659. Same obv. die as 64.
- Obv.* **DNIVSTINI ANVSWIIC**
Rev. **V-ICTOIV-VTONAVI**; in exergue **CONO**
 Tomasini, p. 213, 259 var.
 64. 1.45 g; 15.42 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8662. Same obv. die as 63.
- Obv.* **DNIV?TINI-ANVSPVVC**
Rev. **VICTORIA-ΛVCVSTOR**; in exergue **CONOB**
 Tomasini, p. 218, no. 302 var.
 65. 1.48 g; 15.61 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8665. Same dies as no. 66.
 66. 1.47 g; 14.88 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8666. Same dies as no. 65.

- Obv.* **DNIVSTIINI-ANVSPPAΣ**
Rev. **VICTORI-ΛCVCTOPIAΛ**; in exergue **CONOD**
 Tomasini, p. 218, no. 302 var.
 67. 1.43 g; 15.40 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8679. Scratched on obverse.
- Obv.* **DNIVSTIN-IANVSPPAΣ**
Rev. **VICTOP-ΛVACTOΣ**; in exergue **CONOB**
 Tomasini, p. 218, no. 300 var.
 68. 1.46 g; 14.92 mm; 6mm. Inv. no. 8673. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
- Obv.* **DNVSTIN-VIIVSPIIC**
Rev. **VITOIV-VTOIΛVI**; in exergue **CONOB**
 Similar to Tomasini, p. 211, no. 235.
 69. 1.41 g; 14.17 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8663. Same obverse die as no. 70.
- Obv.* **DNVSTIN VIIVSPIIC**
Rev. **VICTOIV- I-VTONΛVI**; in exergue **CONOB**
 Similar to Tomasini, p. 211, no. 238.
 70. 1.45 g; 14.98 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8664. Same obverse die as no. 69. Scratched on obverse and reverse.
- Obv.* **DNIVSTIN-IANVSPPAV**
Rev. **VICTORI-ΛΛVCVSTI**; in exergue **CONOC**
 Tomasini, p. 218, no. 302 var.
 71. 1.45 g; 15.39 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8674.
- Obv.* **DNIVITINI-ANVSPAVC**
Rev. **VICTRI-ΛVCVSPVI**; in exergue **CIND**
 Tomasini, p. 213, no. 259 var.
 72. 1.46 g; 15.47 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8677.
- Obv.* **DNIVSTI-ISAΛVIC**
Rev. **V-ICTOV**-ITONΛVI**; in exergue **CONOD**
 Tomasini, p. 227 group G JAN 8.
 73. 1.45 g; 14.83 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8672.
- Obv.* **DNIVSTI-NIANVS**
Rev. **V-ICTOAII-IHOT'IAVI**; in exergue **CONOD**
 Similar to Tomasini, p. 213, no. 257.
 74. 1.44 g; 15.54 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8669.
- Obv.* **DNIVSTI-NIANVS**
Rev. **V-ICTOAI-IITOIAVI**; in exergue **CONOD**
 Similar to Tomasini, p. 213, no. 258.
 75. 1.45 g; 15.83 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8661. Small scratch on reverse.
- Obv.* **VITIAI-VITIVIN**
Rev. **CI-VIN-I-VITVNVVI**; in exergue **IONO**
 Tomasini, pp. 225–7, group JAN 8.
 76. 1.46 g; 15.14 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8671. Small scratch on obverse.
- Obv.* **DNIVSTNI-IANPPVA**
Rev. **VIOTVΣ-I-NPOTΣI**; in exergue **CONOD**. Victory walking to the left.
 Tomasini, p. 209, no. 213 var. (Justin I).
 77. 1.46 g; 15.12 mm; 6 h. Inv. no. 8675. Scratched on obverse and reverse.

PLATE 52

PLIEGO, A HOARD OF LATE ROMAN AND VISGOTHIC GOLD (1)

PLATE 54

PLIEGO, A HOARD OF LATE ROMAN AND VISGOTHIC GOLD (3)

PLIEGO, A HOARD OF LATE ROMAN AND VISGOTHIC GOLD (4)

